

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL SCIENCE

Sodikova Nargiza, Tashkent University of Applied Sciences

ANNOTATION

The article provides instructions on the use of innovative technologies in the development of modern lessons in the teaching of physics. **Keywords:** Innovation, creative, technology, also, in this article, the physics science is taught in new methods and the prospects for its development with the introduction of innovative technologies are highlighted.

Key words: innovation, physics, pedagogical technologies, methodical instructions, radical changing

INTRODUCTION .

At present, the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the teaching of subjects in all educational institutions of the country is a topical issue. The rapid development of science and technology is radically changing the content of production in industry and agriculture in our country. A number of professions in modern manufacturing require the training of professionals who are not only well-informed, but also highly developed, have their own thinking and pedagogical skills. The use of any pedagogical technology in the educational process depends on who teaches the student and who the teacher teaches. These pedagogical technology -based exercises allow students to focus on their own thinking, while satisfying their desire to express their involvement in the necessary life achievements and exercises.

MATERIAL AND METHODS.

In order to solve the problems facing the education system in the emerging modern processes, it is necessary to learn new information and assess their own knowledge, to make the necessary decisions, to think independently and freely. Therefore, in the educational process of educational institutions, the role and importance of modern teaching methods, interactive methods and innovative

technologies is great. The knowledge that is relevant to pedagogy and their application in education ensures that practicing students are well-educated and well-rounded. Innovation - (innovation in English) - is the introduction of innovation. Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and the activities of both (teacher and student), and in its implementation are used interactive methods. The curriculum, which seeks to standardize competencies for secondary schools, clearly outlines the competencies and standard levels of compulsory education, daily reading elements that students need to know. The fulfillment of important tasks of education and upbringing of young people depends on the degree to which the teacher's worldview, professionalism, talent and culture are in line with the world. The role of the first lesson is different, taking into account our different experiences in the learning process. An effective lesson can be achieved only if each subject teacher makes the first lesson interesting and lively. The first lesson, which begins with the development of students' interest in the subject, can be a guiding lesson for the student. In this case, with the increase of the student's interest and interest in the subject, the teacher's actions, concise words, and critical thinking take place under the control of the student. The student critically evaluates each of the teacher's actions and imitates their actions. Students will be fascinated by the novelty of the teacher's approach to the lesson. Thus, the ideological and theoretical level of the first lesson should be high and the quality of the lesson should be considered.

RESULTS.

Therefore, the student's interest in the subject can be increased only if the teacher highly evaluates the student, taking in to account the activity of the student in the classroom, completing the question during the lesson, observation, relevant examples from life. The implementation of the new curriculum in the lives of schoolchildren requires the improvement of teaching methods and content, which will be provided to students in the classroom. It is good for the teacher to learn the character of the students during the lesson. For example, if we walk around the classroom, see the work of those who do not make a difference, warn and approve

of their shortcomings, reward others, show them the way, attract the student, he will be satisfied with the teacher, increase his confidence and interest in the subject. In the future, students will be able to study independently, learn the arts and increase their interest in lessons. It consists of teaching students to think independently and to educate in all areas of modern education. We must not forget that teachers, in the first place during the lesson, not only provide students with in-depth knowledge in the teaching of subjects, but also cultivate their interest in science and hard work.

Today, the main task of teachers is not only to educate, but also to properly integrate the educational process, to be able to constantly innovate in the educational process, that is, to seek innovative services. The stages of formation of the innovative activity of the teacher are as follows. The first stage-ready methodical instructions are clearly prepared. The second step is the introduction of new methodological methods. The third step is to fully study the content, methods and types of implementation of the new idea. The fourth stage - the teacher can develop new technologies of teaching and education. Today, the attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is growing. Modern technologies teach students to search for, acquire and analyze the knowledge they have acquired, and even to complete the puzzles themselves. Thus, in order to implement these requirements, each teacher must continue to improve their professional pedagogical skills, for which they must be able to choose the right pedagogical technology.

DISCUSSION.

The use of innovative technologies in physics class will satisfy the desire of young people to express their attitudes to important life achievements and problems, give them the opportunity to think, to justify their views. The content of teaching physics courses can be expressed in different ways:

➤ The teacher's live speech, the main part of his research is devoted to the question of what should be the teacher's speech. The teacher performs this task in

his or her written and oral activities. Because the fluency, conciseness, expressiveness and logic of the teacher's language is a guarantee for the conscious and thorough understanding of the teaching material by students ".

➤ Questions, assignments, problems, cards, visual aids, chain words, programmed materials, tests, etc. are the forms of educational material. It serves the purpose of adapting the process of mastering the topics related to the sections of the physics course to students, the organization, management, control of education. For example, according to the needs of teaching and learning, the subjects of the physics course enter into different forms of educational content and begin to act in the form of educational element, stage (consisting of several elements), period (consisting of several stages). Therefore, each of the learning element, stage and period can be considered as a specific independent didactic phenomenon. In order to teach a didactic phenomenon in the process of teaching the subjects of the physics course, there must be three constant components:

1. Teaching topics for the department (teacher activities). 2
2. . The student's mastery of the topics in the section.
3. 3. Study material.

As a result of the interaction of these components, the educational learning elements, the learning phase consisting of several learning elements and the learning period are formed. In turn, here are the types of interactions that play a role in the development of teaching materials on the topics of the physics course sections: - The influence of the teacher of the topics of the section on the teaching material. In this case, the teacher brings the teaching material on the department in acceptable forms according to the need to study the knowledge of the department of physics. Describe the rules given in physics textbooks, bring the rules to the reader in as simple and interesting forms as possible, introduce the rules, definitions into formulas, diagrams, comparison tables, problem forms; - The impact of each of the modified forms of thematic teaching material on the section is felt in teaching activities. Definitions of physical quantities and their units, representing different views of nature and natural phenomena, make the laws

pertaining to the section easier. As the explanation ensures the popularity of the teacher's speech, the presentation of drawings, tables, learning problems posed by the department and the choice of problem-based learning

CONCLUSION .

The most important thing today is to be able to apply all that they have learned to students in lessons and other educational processes with high skill. It should not be assumed that such educational institutions and teachers should not deviate from the standardization of teaching methods that apply to them at the time and achieve high results, and should use only some kind of pedagogical technology. Through the use of modern pedagogical technologies and innovations in the classroom, the teacher can easily become a legal teacher, that is, not a teacher of the student, but a teacher of learning, mastering, teaching difficult materials. and through the effective application of their pedagogical skills and the continuous improvement of the quality and level of education of students in the acquired competencies.

REFERENCES

1. R. Ishamuhammedov A. Abbdudurov «ta'limda innovatsion texnologiyalar» Toshkent 2008.
2. B. H Rahimov A. Mavlyanov «Pedagogik texnologiyalar sxemalarda» Toshkent 2009
3. A. Mavlanov S. Abdalova L. Yusupova «Zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiya t amollari asosida dars mashg'ulotlarini olib boorish texnologiyasi» Toshkent 2010
4. M.F. Atoyeva. Didactic foundations of inter-media relations in the training of university students. International Scientific Journal. Theoretical & Applied Science. pISSN: 2308-4944 (print) e-ISSN: 2409-0085 (online). Year: 2020 Issue: 06 Volume: 86, P. 124.
5. M.F. Atoyeva, R. Safarova. Pedagogical integration as a means of forming professionally important qualities among students of a medical university. Academia. ISSN: 2249-7137 Vol. 10, Issue 8, August 2020. Impact Factor: SJIF

2020 = 7.13 ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
<https://saarj.com>.

6. Use of alternative energy sources at the natural sciences lessons. SK Kakhkhorov, HO Juraev, MF Atoeva. The Way of Science. 36, 148

7. S Fayziev. Investigation of the magnetic structure of FeBO₃:Mg//III
INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE OF YOUNG RESEARCHERS
1 (1), 105-107.2019

